

WORK RELEASE METROLOGICAL OF SUPPORT ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY .

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Abstract: The article provides information on increasing the economic efficiency of metrological equipment, combining existing measuring instruments with modern measuring instruments, abandoning obsolete instruments and equipment.

Keywords: measurement uncertainty, Monte Carlo method, revision of the “Guide to the Expressing of Uncertainty in Measurement”, kurtosis method

Measure manage during parameter is measured and given the norm with is compared , therefore for suitable or suitable doesn't come This considering the decision as optimal possible not because _ There is an error . Stream in consideration when you get , like this decision acceptance will not be done , as well as real the picture breaks and As a result negative economic consequences take comes (Resource wrong evaluation with depends) [1].

Technological the process control in doing used data to mistakes face comes as a result technological of processes values the most acceptable and technical and economic work release indicators reduces _ Work release of the composition which elements usual work release system in the example measure with consider dependent . _ The system input material, energy , half ready products , ingredients parts service is showing . They are quality parameters and quantitative in the situation access to the right have [2].

Measurement tools while working , well-known expenses and measure normal operation of tools for necessary has been expenses and belongs to capital from the

stakeholder consists of Because Work release metrological provide This is not a branch activity type , some one of the bank industry of investments requirements and profitability in the fields Demand done requirements makes sense would be

Another one important task is this metrological help programs done increase economic efficiency to evaluate possibility giving the only one metrology [3].

So to measure _ situation analysis to do and work release of comparison purposeful planning according to of work economic aspects seeing exit As a result , research of transfer relevance and practicality about conclusion to do possible Directions [4]:

1. Work release metrological technical of service final shape formation ;
2. Technician and economic work release indicators for measure of accuracy effect set [5];
3. Work release metrological support efficiency for criterion justification ;
4. Continuously measure processes metrological support according to of work economic efficiency evaluation for scientific and methodical the basics create ;
5. of measurement measurable parameters nomenclature optimization and economic criterion for of measurements accuracy [6];

Metrological help content analysis to do not only measure the necessity , perhaps complete measure and measure and the product measure and measure completeness , own on time and measure speed to increase directed showed Life rotation all stages - development , development release , tests and operation [7].

Analysis to be done , technologically of processes technological processes and metrological reliability account received without of products methods and quality control of doing accuracy features and quality control of doing accuracy characteristics effect determination offer done measure tools and them check correctness [8].

His efficiency for products Create during measure of quality effect analysis do , defined requirements compatibility affirmative enterprise metrological support elements designation enable gave _ Such elements created products for design documents work release , metrological analysis make (expertise) measure tools , measurement methods , completeness and correctness own into take need was determined of the enterprise all metrological your support all of the elements compatibility complete check almost possible not because _ metrological assumptions metrological in terms of adaptation according to statistics assumptions check order based on selected price methods use offer will be done defined requirements provide [9]. _

When assessing the level of product quality, it is important to take into account economic indicators that describe the differences in the preparation, production and operation of the product or in the field of consumption [10].

Economic indicators are costs for the preparation and testing of experimental samples, the cost of product production, the costs of operating technical facilities, etc .

Quality metrics may or may not have dimensions like physical metrics. Quantitative description of quality indicators means their measurements in certain units [11].

For example, the cost of labor used to produce a product is the time spent to produce a unit of product, expressed in man-hours. Expressing the labor cost in working days does not change the labor cost of the product [12].

Similarly, the expression of economic indicators such as the cost or price of a product in sums or other units does not change its value [13]. Like physical quantities, the quantity of qualitative indicators can be expressed by absolute and relative quantities [14]. The absolute value of physical quantities always has dimension, while relative quantities are dimensionless. Absolute measures of product quality can be dimensionless or dimensionless, while relative measures are always dimensionless [15].

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